

Leveraging Retrieval-Augmented In-context Learning for Complex Air Traffic Scenario Generation

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Abstract—Efficient and customizable air traffic scenario generation is crucial for advancing research and enabling the evaluation of advanced air traffic management (ATM) concepts, as well as supporting the strategic development of future ATM systems. Traditional methods for air traffic scenario generation rely heavily on modifying historical data, creating randomized traffic, or hand-crafting specific scenarios. However, these approaches are time-consuming and offer limited customizability in tailoring specific research or operational needs, such as testing novel ATM concepts or human-in-the-loop (HITL) experiments involving complex air traffic scenarios. This paper proposes a novel methodology that leverages large language models (LLMs) and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) to dynamically generate traffic scenarios for high-fidelity air traffic simulations based on natural language inputs. It allows users to seamlessly create and modify traffic scenarios with ease, significantly reducing the time and effort involved in traditional methods. The system supports iterative customization, enabling rapid adaptation of traffic densities, routes, separations, aircraft types, and operational constraints to generate complex air traffic scenarios. In experimental evaluations, the performance of Command R, Llama3.1-8b-Instruct, and GPT-4o-mini was compared for a list of prompts with varying complexity. Command R demonstrated superior performance, achieving 100% syntactic accuracy and the highest semantic accuracy. By streamlining scenario generation and enhancing user interaction, this methodology provides a valuable tool for advancing ATM research, training, and operational planning.

Keywords—Air traffic simulation, large language models (LLMs), generative artificial intelligence (GenAI), complex air traffic scenarios, air transportation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Air traffic scenarios constitute a fundamental component of exploratory research in air traffic management (ATM), underpinning concept validation, rapid prototyping, and the assessment of novel methodologies. They serve as critical tools for advanced ATM concept evaluations, human-in-the-loop (HITL) experiments, and testing frameworks aimed at refining conflict detection and resolution algorithms [1], [2]. The capability to systematically generate and iteratively refine air traffic scenarios based on experimental feedback is indispensable across various phases of ATM research and development, spanning from initial concept exploration to pre-operational validation, system integration, and air traffic controller (ATCO) training programs [3].

Historically, a range of simulation environments has been employed in air transportation research to facilitate air traffic

scenario generation. High-fidelity simulation platforms such as ESCAPE and BlueSky [4], [5], along with several medium- and low-fidelity environments [6], have been utilized to construct air traffic flows through hand-crafted or randomly generated traffic data. In many instances, historical datasets such as ADS-B records have been modified by altering flight levels, departure times, routing structures, or separation parameters to synthesize specific target scenarios.

Despite their utility, these conventional approaches exhibit significant limitations. The manual modification of historical data or the generation of new flight plans for simulations is inherently time-intensive, requires substantial human effort [7], and is constrained by the availability of relevant data. Additionally, scenario generation that relies on historical records inherently replicates existing traffic patterns, restricting the ability to create diverse, novel, or edge-case scenarios [8].

Furthermore, the efficiency of these methods is heavily influenced by the expertise of the user. Researchers and air traffic subject matter experts (SMEs) with limited simulation proficiency must invest considerable time or rely on external assistance to construct scenarios that align with their investigative objectives [3]. As such, an advanced, adaptable scenario generation framework is imperative to expedite the transition from conceptualization to simulation and evaluation. This need is particularly pronounced for testing emerging ATM paradigms, investigating extreme operational edge cases, and analyzing human performance in next-generation human-machine interaction environments. A more intuitive and intelligent approach to scenario generation would empower researchers and SMEs to construct operationally relevant scenarios based on domain expertise without necessitating specialized simulation skills.

Recent advancements in generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) have transformed user interactions with systems. This transformation has been driven by the availability of pre-trained large language models (LLMs) that excel in general reasoning, natural language inference, sentiment analysis, semantic understanding, and content generation [9]. Leveraging the interactive capabilities and natural language understanding of such models, they can be customized for domain-specific requirements such as the generation of user-specified and customized traffic scenarios. This approach holds significant potential in streamlining the generation and customization of simulated air traffic, wherein specific user requirements

can be accommodated by the model, reducing the time and effort traditionally associated with these tasks. The interactive nature of the model can be used to enhance or modify the generated scenarios with ease.

This paper presents a novel methodology that uses natural language instructions to instantly generate customizable air traffic scenarios suitable for high-fidelity simulations. By converting user inputs into detailed, realistic scenarios, our approach improves the flexibility and usability of simulation tools, enabling intuitive and adaptive scenario creation for research, training, and operational planning. The methodology outputs scenario parameters in JSON format, that is post processed according to the specific simulation environment. This work leverages NARSIM, a high-fidelity simulator developed by the Netherlands Aerospace Centre (NLR) [10]. The methodology demonstrates semantic understanding across diverse input levels, generating syntactically correct output executable in the simulation environment. Furthermore, the user-model interaction allows for quick scenario refinement based on user feedback.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Scenario Generation in Air Transportation

A typical scenario generation process adapted from Alam et al. [11] is illustrated in Figure 1. The process of generating air traffic scenarios is initiated by clearly defining the objectives and scope, which are directly informed by the underlying research hypothesis or operational needs. The objectives may include performance assessment of ATM systems or algorithms under different traffic conditions, ATCO behavior evaluation in different traffic scenarios, decision support tool evaluation, etc. This stage typically involves close collaboration between scenario developers (SDs) and Subject Matter Experts (SMEs) to refine and formalize the objectives in alignment with real-world constraints and research goals. The next phase involves the determination of scenario evaluation metrics, which serve as benchmarks for assessing the validity and relevance of the scenario. Following this, the scenario’s specific attributes such as traffic density, aircraft performance profiles, separation minima, operational conditions, and identified congestion points—must be rigorously defined along with any assumptions and limitations inherent to the scenario. Given the complexity of these characteristics, the data collection phase often presents significant challenges due to the proprietary nature of operational data and its dispersed availability across multiple sources. Once the required data is acquired, sophisticated data processing and scenario modification algorithms are deployed to modify the data and curate the initial scenario. The resulting preliminary scenario undergoes a detailed inspection and iterative refinement to progressively align it with the required parameters and objectives. Each iteration may involve adjusting specific variables or inputs, followed by further validation. Before final deployment in the simulation environment, the scenario is validated by SMEs, ensuring its operational soundness. Thus, the entire scenario generation process is inherently iterative, involving substantial computational resources, and is subject to constraints such as data availability and the

Figure 1: An illustration of a typical scenario generation process involving the scenario developer and the SME, highlighting the iterative processes involved in generating a traffic scenario.

technical expertise of the SDs. For the evaluation of advanced operational concepts or novel procedures, where operational data is often unavailable, developers must rely on randomized scenario generation techniques. This approach leverages probabilistic distributions for key parameters such as traffic density, aircraft types, and routing structures. In this context, traffic scenarios are generated based on specified distributions that reflect operationally plausible yet novel traffic behaviors. Despite the differences in data origin, the subsequent stages of scenario development, including iterative refinement and computational optimization, mirror those in traditional methods. Given the stochastic nature of the input data, generating such scenarios requires extensive computational expertise to ensure the process remains resource-efficient while meeting the desired scenario characteristics. Consequently, most ATM research adopts one of these approaches. Conflict detection and resolution studies frequently employ randomized generation in abstract settings to train and evaluate models [2], [12]. Similarly, novel operational paradigms, such as free route airspace (FRA) [13] and flow-centric operations [14], use distribution-based randomization for scenario generation. For example, Sunil et al. [13] apply uniform distributions to flight paths and headings, while Guleria et al. [14] use historical data-driven normal distributions for aircraft speeds. While such methods enable large-scale scenario generation, ensuring data quality and handling outliers remains a challenge.

In contrast, studies on continuous descent operations [15], arrival sequencing [16], and demand-capacity balancing [17] often rely on historical data. However, extensive modifications are required to adapt the data for experimental purposes, making the process time-consuming and constrained by original data distributions. Human-in-the-loop (HITL) experiments and ATCO training further necessitate customized scenario generation tailored to specific use cases [3], [18]. To facilitate this, an Aviation Scenario Definition Language (ASDL) [19] has been proposed, allowing domain experts to construct scenarios with predefined inputs. While ASDL

reduces technical barriers, scenario creation remains labor-intensive, particularly for generating multiple aircraft and complex traffic configurations.

To gain deeper insights into the workflows, challenges, and practical approaches in air traffic scenario generation, we conducted interviews with four experts specializing in ATM and computational modeling, with a minimum of 7 years of research and training experience in the domain. Their feedback emphasized an iterative and systematic process similar to that depicted in Figure 1, with key challenges in speed, and accuracy of scenario generation and customization. When required scenarios diverge significantly from available historical data, extensive modifications are often necessary. Adjusting parameters such as traffic density, aircraft trajectories, start times, or operational constraints can be both labor-intensive and error-prone, with inaccuracies in parameter tuning potentially resulting in scenarios that fail to meet intended objectives necessitating further refinements.

These challenges are particularly evident in complex, non-nominal scenarios (e.g., high-traffic conditions, adverse weather, and safety-critical events). Conflict scenario generation, for instance, requires a nuanced understanding of the operational context and extensive manual customization of individual parameters, modeling diverse conflict permutations, accounting for interdependencies among aircraft states, making realistic scenario design highly intricate. Due to these difficulties, compromises often lead to oversimplified scenarios that fail to capture operational complexities.

These findings highlight the pressing need for advanced tools to optimize scenario-generation workflows. Such tools could streamline the process by minimizing manual effort, enabling the efficient creation of diverse, high-quality scenarios that align with specific objectives. By embedding sophisticated customization and refinement capabilities, these tools can facilitate a more dynamic, adaptable approach, reducing bottlenecks and enhancing the agility of scenario development processes. Figure 2 highlights this research idea that involves interaction between the user and the language model which is capable of retrieving domain-specific knowledge to generate complex air traffic scenarios based on the user prompts. This approach also enable refinement/customization of the generated scenarios through access to the conversation history between the model and the user.

B. Large Language Models

Mainstream LLMs are based on the Transformer architecture [20] that created a paradigm shift in generative artificial intelligence. Transformers rely on self-attention mechanisms that are crucial in capturing the textual nuances in natural language. LLMs have demonstrated remarkable success in diverse application areas such as natural language processing and machine translation [21] and content generation [22]. Use cases of LLMs in finance [23], healthcare [24], and software development [25] have been successfully demonstrated.

The applications of LLMs in aviation are also being explored. Due to the safety-critical nature of the aviation domain, research has been limited to non-safety-critical aspects of air transportation. Ray et al. [26] used ChatGPT for

Figure 2: Overall concept diagram that highlights the user-model interaction through the input prompts and LLM output, and air transportation specific information retrieval through retrieval augmented generation (RAG).

aviation safety analysis to generate incident report synopsis based on the provided narratives. Along similar lines, Abdulhak et al. [27] have leveraged the fundamental strength of language models i.e. understanding and summarization of text, to assist air traffic managers in summarizing historical ground delay program (GDP) information. Recently, Wang et al. [28] fine-tuned the Llama-2 model for multiple tasks such as question answering, content creation, summarizing, and similarity search based on the data used to tune the model.

While LLMs exhibit strong performance in the aforementioned tasks, their generative potential in air transportation remains largely unexplored. As discussed, research on evaluating novel concepts of operations, assessing model performance, and conducting human-in-the-loop experiments has primarily relied on modifying historical data or employing randomized traffic generation. These approaches are limited in their adaptability, making it challenging to incorporate user-defined constraints, modify scenarios dynamically, and efficiently generate tailored traffic data.

To address these limitations, this research proposes an LLM-driven methodology for generating customized air traffic scenarios based on natural language inputs. The approach focuses on scenario generation within a specified en-route sector, adhering to operational airway structures. Generated aircraft trajectories conform to the Base of Aircraft Data (BADA 3.7) performance model, ensuring realism and operational validity.

III. METHODOLOGY

Figure 3 presents the research methodology, which adapts a foundational large language model for the air traffic domain using retrieval-augmented generation (RAG). By integrating domain-specific data retrieval, RAG enhances the model's response quality for user queries. The model generates scenario-specific parameters in JSON format, which are subsequently converted into the required XML format during post-processing. This methodology aims to produce executable code for simulation environments based on conversational inputs while enabling real-time user interaction for scenario refinement. Detailed descriptions of each component are provided in the following subsections.

Figure 3: The proposed methodology employs Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) to extract sector specific information—airways, waypoints, and aircraft types from domain-specific documents, facilitating tailored air traffic scenarios generation

A. Large Language Model

The Command R model, with 35 billion parameters and developed by Cohere, was chosen for its exceptional capability to process long-context inputs—a critical requirement for Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) pipelines managing extensive domain-specific data. Unlike many LLMs that encounter the “lost in the middle” phenomenon where information from the middle of lengthy texts is overlooked or inaccurately retrieved, Command R excels at maintaining coherent comprehension across the entire input sequence. This strength ensures effective integration of the full chat history, retrieved RAG data, and user prompts into its responses. Additionally, its open-source nature and relatively low computational demand (24GB of VRAM), supported by Cohere’s free API position Command R as an ideal choice for projects requiring scalable, accurate, and resource-efficient solutions, particularly in complex domains where long-context understanding is paramount.

B. Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)

Conventional large language models (LLMs) are pre-trained on diverse corpora without specialization in any specific domain. To adapt them for domain-specific tasks such as air traffic scenario generation, two primary customization approaches exist: fine-tuning and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG). Fine-tuning involves modifying the model’s weights using a labeled dataset, which is often difficult to acquire in specialized fields like air transportation. Additionally, fine-tuning large models is computationally expensive and time-intensive. RAG, by contrast, allows an LLM to retrieve and incorporate external domain-specific data without modifying its underlying parameters. This approach incurs minimal computational cost, primarily from embedding domain-specific documents (discussed further in Section IV-A). RAG has been shown to mitigate hallucinations and errors [29], [30], while also enabling seamless model updates by simply modifying the document repository, eliminating the need for retraining. Given these advantages, the RAG methodology

was chosen to customize Command R and other models used for performance evaluation.

To enhance the model’s task-specific capabilities, a structured system message was incorporated. This message serves as an initial directive, guiding the model’s behavior, establishing operational constraints, and defining the required output format [31]. Upon receiving a user prompt, the system retrieves relevant information snippets from the vector store (as illustrated in Figure 3) and inserts them after the system message but before the user’s query. This enables the model to utilize domain-specific context when generating responses. In multi-turn interactions, previous conversations are retained as part of the input context, ensuring continuity. Figure 4 illustrates the information that cumulatively forms the input context for the model. The system message was carefully

Figure 4: Contents of the input context that include the system message, chat history, information retrieved from additional documents and the user’s input prompt.

designed to specify detailed instructions, including the output schema, directives to use RAG-extracted data for scenario generation, and constraints limiting aircraft selection to pre-defined types. The output schema was structured as a JSON template, encapsulating all parameters necessary for traffic generation, thereby facilitating streamlined post-processing compared to free-text outputs. The complete input context for the LLM consists of the system message, user query, RAG-retrieved information, and chat history.

C. Retrieval with Maximal Marginal Relevance

Maximal Marginal Relevance (MMR) [32] retrieval technique was used in this work. MMR optimizes information

retrieval by balancing the relevance of retrieved items to the query and diversity in the results to minimize redundancy among the selected items. This allows for greater customization in the diversity and relevance of the retrieved documents. It prioritizes selecting documents that are both highly relevant to a query and minimally redundant with the already retrieved documents which is beneficial for prompts with varying levels of abstraction. The MMR score for a candidate item D_i is calculate as follows:

$$\text{MMR}(D_i) = \lambda \text{Rel}(D_i, Q) - (1 - \lambda) \max_{D_j \in S} \text{Sim}(D_i, D_j)$$

where:

- $\text{Rel}(D_i, Q)$: Relevance of the candidate D_i to the query Q .
- $\text{Sim}(D_i, D_j)$: Similarity between the candidate D_i and any already-selected item D_j .
- S : The set of items already selected.
- λ : A trade-off parameter ($0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$) that balances relevance and diversity.

Here, relevance and similarity are measured using cosine similarity.

IV. DATA PREPARATION

A. Data Preparation for RAG

Figure 5 highlights the sector (Sector 6) and the corresponding airways of the Singapore FIR in consideration. The input document is a text-based PDF containing airways in Sector 6 and the coordinates of waypoints inside the sector and its vicinity. Context extracted from this document serves

Figure 5: Sector 6 and the corresponding airways that were included in the RAG document. The arrows indicate the airway direction.

as an additional input for the LLM. The document is designed to match the required JSON output format, as other formats, such as natural language and tables, led to poor syntactic conformance. Each airway includes parameters like initialization time, aircraft type, departure and destination airfields, initial position (latitude, longitude, altitude, heading), and waypoints. For example, the parameters for airway M758 are shown in **Dataset sample 1**, providing a logical path for flights. A separator ('- - - -') is used between airway sections to facilitate accurate text chunking.

Dataset sample 1: Information of Airway M758 as in the document used in RAG.

```
1. Airway M758
{
  "time": "Initialization time of aircraft
after simulation start in seconds",
  "type": "A320",
  "departure": {"af": "WMKK"},
  "initial_position": {
    "latitude": "024802.00N",
    "longitude": "1024019.00E",
    "altitude": "FL370",
    "heading": "87.11"
  },
  "air_route": [
    "SAROX", "PADLI", "IDSEL", "URIGO", "
VISAT", "MABAL",
    "ELGOR", "OPULA", "LUSMO", "TERIX", "
OLKIT"
  ],
  "destination": {"af": "WBKK"}
}
```

Figure 6 outlines the process of constructing the RAG database. First, the PDF document was parsed using the *UnstructuredPDFLoader* module from Langchain [33]. The text was then split into chunks using Langchain's *RecursiveCharacterTextSplitter*, with a chunk size of 550 and overlap of 100, optimized for single airway information. Clear separators are recommended in PDFs to assist the splitter. The chunks were embedded using the *mxbai-embed-large* model [34], a fast-performing embedding model excelling on the Massive Text Embedding Benchmark (MTEB). Finally, the embeddings were stored in a vector database for LLM retrieval.

Figure 6: RAG database construction process.

B. Prompt Design

Interaction with the model is facilitated through conversational-style prompts from the user. Three levels of prompts, or 'abstractions' (Table I), were designed to incorporate varying degrees of detail into the scenario. For example, a Level 1 abstraction generates a randomized traffic scenario with minimal user input, while Level 3 allows for highly customized, specific scenarios based on the user's detailed requirements. The model was configured to generate randomized traffic scenarios based on three distinct traffic density levels, specified as follows:

- Type 1 traffic: 1 to 4 aircraft.
- Type 2 traffic: 5 to 9 aircraft.
- Type 3 traffic: 10 to 20 aircraft.

Table II shows examples of prompts used to interact with the selected model. Rather than adhering to a pre-defined template of text, the user can incorporate natural language

TABLE I. Prompt abstraction levels and their corresponding example prompts for generating traffic scenarios.

Abstraction	Prompt Definition
Level 1	Specify the Type of traffic scenario to generate. <i>Example prompt:</i> Generate a Type 1 traffic density scenario in sector 6.
Level 2	Specify the number of aircraft to generate. <i>Example prompt:</i> Generate 4 aircraft in sector 6.
Level 3	Specify the number of aircraft, the type of aircraft, the corresponding airways, and the aircraft initiation time, and the separation time between aircraft. <i>Example prompt:</i> Generate 4 aircraft in sector 6 on airways M758, N884, N892, and N875 . The first aircraft should start at time 100 seconds . All the aircraft should be separated by 200 seconds .

style communication in the prompts. Further, the user can also request information from the model relating to the characteristics of the sector and the content of the RAG document as shown in base prompts 4 and 5 of Table II, and the customizable traffic scenario features in Table III.

TABLE II. Examples of prompts used to interact with language model.

S.no	Base prompts
1	Generate a Type 3 traffic scenario in sector 6.
2	Generate a traffic scenario with 12 aircraft. The aircraft should initiate at time 0 seconds. If the aircraft are on the same air route, ensure that they are 100 seconds apart.
3	Generate an 8 aircraft traffic scenario in sector 6. 4 aircraft should be on airway N892 separated by 300 seconds with the first aircraft initializing at 0 seconds. The other 4 aircraft should be on airway M771R, separated by 150 seconds, starting at time 50.
4	What is the number of aircraft in a Type 2 traffic scenario?
5	Give me the information of airway M771.
Customization prompts	
1	Modify the previous scenario so that the aircraft are separated by 100 seconds.
2	To the previous output, add 3 aircraft on airway M761 separated by 300 seconds, with the first aircraft starting at time 0.
3	Ensuring that all the information in the previous output is the same, add a new aircraft on airway M771 at an initialization of 150 seconds. Merge this with the previous output into a single JSON file.

TABLE III. Customizable traffic scenario features.

S.no	Scenario features
1.	The number of aircraft in the scenario.
2.	The type of aircraft in the scenario.
3.	The start time of the simulation i.e the first aircraft appearing in the simulation.
4.	Separation between the aircraft (time-based).
5.	Airways of the aircraft.
6.	Flight level of the aircraft.

C. Retriever and Model Parameters

For the experiments, the MMR (refer Section III-C) search was implemented using Langchain [33]. The search param-

eters include $fetch_k$, k , and λ . The $fetch_k$ parameter determines the initial number of chunks considered for similarity checking and was set to 28 to ensure that all document chunks are included. The k parameter represents the number of chunks sent to the model after the similarity check and was set to 16 to capture most if not all the airway information. Finally, the λ parameter balances the trade-off between relevance and diversity in the search results, with λ at 1 giving more weight to relevance and 0 emphasizing diversity among the selected results. After multiple iterations, it was set to 0.6. The temperature parameter controls the randomness of the model's output, with a value of 0 leading to more deterministic responses and a value of 1 resulting in more diverse and creative outputs. To eliminate variability in the experiments, the temperature was set to 0.

D. Scenario Feasibility Assurance

To guarantee the feasibility of generated scenarios, the system enforces an initial condition requiring all aircraft to be at least 100 seconds apart at the scenario's start, as a guardrail. 100 seconds in an en-route airspace corresponds to approximately 12.5 nautical miles at 450 knots. This measure prevents conflicts and ensures operational validity from the outset, providing a reliable foundation for subsequent scenario adjustments. By embedding this constraint into the system message, the process aligns with the broader goal of generating robust traffic scenarios efficiently, minimizing the need for error-prone manual corrections.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Model Performance Comparison

The model performance was evaluated in terms of the syntactic and semantic accuracy for the corresponding input prompts. For this work, these two metrics are defined as follows. Syntactic accuracy refers to the correctness of the generated output file for the simulation environment. In other words, the outputs from the models that were correctly and completely runnable in the simulation environment were scored as 1, otherwise 0. Syntactic accuracy was tested on prompts 1 to 12 in the **Appendix 1**. Semantic accuracy refers to the degree to which the generated air traffic scenarios align with the user's input prompts in terms of specified features and constraints. In other words, the number of features (based on Table III) requested by the user that were incorporated in the output by the model. Semantic accuracy was tested for all the prompts in the appendix. As such the maximum score for this metric was 48. This is because different prompts required different numbers of characteristics and constraints. The performance of Command R was compared to two other models, Llama3.1-8b-instruct from META and GPT-4o-mini from OpenAI. The Llama3.1-8b-instruct is an open-source model fine-tuned for instructions following and conversation-style tasks. GPT-4o-mini is a proprietary model from OpenAI (model weights and size are not available) and requires paid subscriptions for API access. Both of these models were tested using an API key from Groq [35]. For these evaluations, the models' chat history was reset after every generated output. This was done to ensure that the context window limits

Figure 7: An interactive interface developed to enable seamless user interaction with the scenario generation model. The interface allows for document upload, model selection, prompt input, RAG data and chat history visualization and output file download.

of such small-scale models are not breached. Furthermore, it would also provide insights into the retrieval capabilities of the models from the system message and the document used for RAG without the influence of additional context.

In terms of the correctness of the output (Figure 8 (a)), while Llama3.1-8b-Instruct and Command R generate correct outputs for all prompts, GPT-4o-mini failed to generate the correct syntax for two prompts, prompt 5 and prompt 9. In these cases, the model incorrectly extracted the origin and destination airports for the aircraft, as detailed in Data Sample 1, resulting in the affected aircraft not appearing during the simulation run.

Figure 8: Model performance comparison for syntactic accuracy (a) and semantic accuracy (b) for the list of prompts in Appendix 1. The dashed lines indicate the prompts where the models generated partially or completely incorrect outputs.

Figure 8 (b) shows the results for the semantic accuracy of the models. Prompts 6, 9, and 11 were common among the three models wherein these models were unable to incorporate prompt instructions. Based on the required characteristics of the scenario the maximum scores on these prompts were 4, 6, and 7. The models, Llama3.1-8b-Instruct, GPT-4o-mini, and Command R achieved scores of 3, 3, and 3 out of 4 for prompt 6, scores of 2, 3, and 4 out of 6 for prompt 9, and scores of 3,

3 and 3 out of 7 for prompt 11 respectively. This indicates the limitations of these models in handling complex prompts in a single conversation. Furthermore, for Level 1 abstraction level prompts (prompts 4 and 8) both Llama3.1-8b-instruct and the GPT-4o-mini did not generate the correct output (interpreting Type 2 and Type 3 as 2 and 3 aircraft, respectively). This indicates the limitations of these models in extracting relevant information from longer systems messages as compared to Command R. All three models also showed inconsistencies when prompts required generation of aircraft on bi-directional airways such as M758/M758R and M771/M771R, wherein airway M758 was misinterpreted as M758R, potentially due to the high similarity between these two words.

For prompts 13 to 22 which required the models to extract information from the system message and the RAG document, Llama3.1-8b-Instruct and GPT-4o-mini did not provide correct details of the airways and the waypoints for prompts 16,17 and 18. The overall accuracy scores demonstrate that Command R is a more suitable model for the task of scenario generation, given the requirement of information retrieval and scenario customization through conversation-style interactions with the model.

B. Scenario Customization

To investigate whether the models could correctly generate the desired outputs for complex prompts, scenario customization was adopted, which allowed the user to modify the initially generated traffic scenario through multiple interactions with the model. As such, the complex, single prompts were replaced by sequential prompts as demonstrated through an example in Figure 9. For the first scenario, the objective was to create arrival traffic flows into Singapore through the sector (through airways N892 and M771R) and the interaction of these flows with two crossing flows (through airways M761 and M758R) that are added into the scenario subsequently.

Figure 9: An example demonstrating a complex prompt (left) that led to incorrect output and an effective sequential prompt (right) leading to correct output.

As shown in Figure 10, the number of aircraft in the scenario increases from 4 (Type 1 traffic density) in the first output to 13 aircraft (Type 3 traffic density) in the final output. For such specific prompts with subsequent modification, GPT-4o-mini and Command R successfully demonstrated correct scenario generation for 5 individual runs each. These models generated the required traffic scenarios through access to sufficient chat history to enable scenario customization over multiple iterations. This also indicates that increasing the complexity of the traffic scenario in terms of the traffic density can be achieved with relative ease, through sequential prompts to the model. On the other hand, Llama3.1-8b-Instruct failed to generate more than eight aircraft across five attempts. This limitation can be attributed to the model’s restricted context length, which determines the maximum number of tokens (units of text such as words, subwords, or characters) it can process in a single input-output sequence. The model’s context encompasses all information it ‘sees’ during generation, including system instructions, prior conversation history, user queries, and its own outputs. While optimized for conversational tasks, its constrained context capacity makes it unsuitable for complex scenario customization. In the second scenario, a Level 1 abstraction (Table 1) was used to generate a Type 2 traffic scenario and modify it by changing aircraft types. While Llama3.1-8b-Instruct and Command R correctly extracted the number of aircraft and modified the scenario as prompted, GPT-4o-mini consistently generated only two aircraft, failing the customization test. This issue likely stemmed from the model’s inability to interpret ‘Type 2 traffic’ within the long system message and input context. Overall, Command R demonstrated superior semantic and syntactic accuracy, excelling in iterative scenario customization, making it the most suitable model for this task.

C. Model Consistency Across Prompt Complexity Levels

Since Command R demonstrated relatively better retrieval and output generation capability, it was tested for its consistency in output generation. The scenarios in Appendix 1 (except prompts 6, 9, and 11) were categorized into different levels of complexity based on the number of output categories requested, the number of aircraft required, and the amount of variation in airways required. All these factors are associated with the retrieval capabilities of the model and its capability to

generate larger output tokens without missing the information in the prompt. This complexity is, thus, interpreted from the model’s perspective. Table IV shows the categorization of prompts in Appendix 1. Each prompt was tested for 50 iterations. Before each iteration, the chat history and vector database were reset to remove any additional context to the model and ensure that the context input to the model did not accumulate over the iterations.

While the model is highly consistent in generating correct output for Level 1 and Level 2 complexity prompts, the performance decreases, and the number of required characteristics and the number of aircraft increases. The errors are significant in cases where different airways are required along with other constraints. While for all the complexity levels, the number of aircraft generated is correct, errors such as incorrect distribution of aircraft on the desired airways, incomplete airways retrieval (missing waypoints), and in some cases incorrect airway selection become more prevalent. Nonetheless, these errors can be mitigated by sequentially adding traffic to the scenario.

TABLE IV. Prompts in Appendix 1 and their associated complexity.

Complexity	Outputs characteristics	Prompts
Level 1	1 (Type 1 Type 2 traffic)	1, 2, 4, 5
Level 2	Low traffic, same airway, multiple constraints	7
Level 3	Low traffic, multiple airways, and constraints	3
Level 4	High traffic, single constraint	8, 10
Level 5	high traffic, multiple constraints	12

VI. CONCLUSION

This research presents a novel methodology that leverages retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) and large language models to streamline the generation of complex and customizable air traffic scenarios. By enabling natural language interactions and iterative scenario refinement, the proposed approach addresses the limitations of traditional scenario generation methods, including the time-consuming nature of manual data modifications and the constraints imposed by historical data patterns. Experimental evaluations demonstrate that Command R achieves high syntactic and semantic accuracy while supporting dynamic scenario customization across diverse traffic densities and operational requirements. These capabilities make it particularly valuable for advanced air traffic management (ATM) research, concept validation, pre-operational trials, and human-in-the-loop experiments. By allowing domain experts to interact with the model intuitively, this methodology reduces the technical expertise required, empowering researchers to create realistic and operationally relevant scenarios with greater efficiency.

While the scenarios are generated for a high-fidelity simulation environment considering operational routes, there is significant potential for improvement. Future extensions of this work will aim to incorporate geospatial reasoning and improved architecture for conflict scenario generation, multi-modal input capabilities, and improved information retrieval techniques to further improve its performance and applicability to more complex traffic scenarios and simulation

Figure 10: Scenario customization by addition of a specific number of aircraft on designated airways, with defined start times and aircraft separation, across multiple interactions with the model.

Figure 11: Consistency of Command R in generating correct outputs across different complexity levels. Typically, constraints involving relatively longer outputs and diverse constraints affect the model performance negatively.

environments. Leveraging historical flight data and weather patterns to generate operationally more realistic scenarios is also a more challenging yet beneficial extension of this work.

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APPENDIX

Input prompts listed below were used for model evaluation. These prompts were designed to cover the different traffic density types and abstraction levels. Prompts 13 and beyond evaluated the information retrieval capabilities of the models under consideration.

- 1) Generate a Type 1 traffic scenario in sector 6.
- 2) Generate 3 aircraft in sector 6.
- 3) Generate 3 aircraft on airway M758, airway N884 and airway M761. The aircraft should be separated by 200 seconds with the first aircraft starting at 100 seconds.
- 4) Generate a Type 2 traffic scenario in sector 6.
- 5) Generate 6 aircraft in sector 6.
- 6) Generate a 6-aircraft scenario where 3 aircraft are on airway M758 and 3 aircraft are on airway N884. The aircraft should be separated by 300 seconds.
- 7) Generate 4 aircraft on airway M771 separated by 150 seconds. Two aircraft should be A320 and two aircraft B737.
- 8) Generate a Type 3 traffic scenario in sector 6.
- 9) Generate a 12 aircraft scenario where 3 of these aircraft are on airway M758, 5 aircraft on airway N884 and 4 aircraft on airway M771. The starting time should be 0. The aircraft should be separated by 200 seconds. Ensure to use correct airways and output in the correct JSON format.
- 10) Generate 12 aircraft in sector 6.
- 11) Generate 7 aircraft in sector 6. 4 aircraft should be A333 on airway L635 separated by 200 seconds. 3 aircraft should be B737 on airway N884 and separated by 100 seconds.
- 12) Generate a 12 aircraft scenario in sector 6. All aircraft should be A388 and separated by 150 seconds. The first aircraft should start at time 0.
- 13) Give me the information of airway M771.
- 14) What is the last waypoint of airway M771 in the data bundle?
- 15) How many airways are there in the data bundle?
- 16) List all the airway names available in the data bundle.
- 17) How many waypoints are there in the data bundle?
- 18) How many aircraft are available for selection?
- 19) Give me the coordinates of waypoints KILOT, MUMSO, and SAROX.

- 20) Does the data bundle contain airway N994?
- 21) Does the data bundle contain the waypoint ASTRA?
- 22) Give me the information of waypoint ASTRA from the data bundle.